

THE POSSIBILITIES ON THE USE OF THE SPEARMAN CORRELATION COEFFICIENT

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***Abstract.** The Spearman correlation coefficient, sometimes called the rank correlation coefficient, which can be considered an accurate term, is used relatively often in the practice of statistical research and in statistics didactics. It often happens that the term 'rank correlation coefficient' is used, which raises elementary reservations. The Spearman correlation coefficient is a special case of the Pearson correlation coefficient for a pair of random variables with observations expressed as sequences of n natural numbers. Natural numbers cannot be equated with ranks, however. Natural numbers, in this case classified as the results of quotient measurement, are not equivalent to ranks, which result from measurement in a weak (ordinal) scale. This means that the Spearman correlation coefficient cannot be used for rank analysis, but for natural numbers only.*

In the practice of statistical research, the need to analyze the results of rank measurement arises relatively often. The Spearman correlation coefficient, sometimes called the rank-order correlation coefficient or the rank correlation coefficient, is one of the primary tools for such result analysis. While the term

'rank-order' is acceptable, the use of the term 'rank correlation coefficient' for the Spearman correlation coefficient is inaccurate. Appropriate transformation of the Pearson correlation coefficient for a pair of detailed series with observations expressed as strings of natural numbers yields the Spearman correlation coefficient.

It has long been known that the Spearman correlation coefficient is a special case of the Pearson correlation coefficient. The Spearman case concerns a pair of sequences of natural numbers, which inherently belong to ratio scale measurement results. The physical similarity of a sequence of n natural numbers to a sequence of n ranks results in the erroneous treatment of ranks as strong scale measurement results. As such, the Spearman correlation coefficient is commonly misused in the literature as a rank correlation coefficient. This fails to recognize the equivalence of the Spearman's and Pearson's correlation coefficients. Treating the Spearman correlation coefficient as a rank correlation coefficient results in direct application of the Pearson correlation coefficient to rank measurement, which many researchers fail to note.

Keywords: *rank measurement, measurement scales, Spearman correlation coefficient, Pearson correlation coefficient*

Introduction

In the practice of statistical research, the need to analyze the results of rank measurement arises relatively often. The Spearman correlation coefficient, sometimes called the rank-order correlation coefficient or the rank correlation coefficient, is one of the primary tools for such result analysis. While the term 'rank-order' is acceptable, the use of the term 'rank correlation coefficient' for the Spearman correlation coefficient is inaccurate. Appropriate transformation of the

Pearson correlation coefficient for a pair of detailed series with observations expressed as strings of natural numbers yields the Spearman correlation coefficient.

The spearman correlation coefficient specifics

The so-called Spearman ‘rank correlation coefficient’, commonly used in such situations, has been transformed from the Pearson correlation coefficient for the case of sequences of a pair of natural numbers with n observations. The Pearson correlation coefficient, written in its general form:

$$\rho = \frac{\text{cov}(x_i, x_j)}{\sqrt{\text{var}(x_i) \text{var}(x_j)}} \quad (1)$$

takes the following form for the pair of variables X_i and X_j :

$$r_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (x_{it} - \bar{x}_i)(x_{jt} - \bar{x}_j)}{\sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^n (x_{it} - \bar{x}_i)^2 (x_{jt} - \bar{x}_j)^2}}. \quad (2)$$

When the observations on the variables X_i and X_j are natural numbers (Obviously, observations in the form of natural numbers don't act as ranks here but are numbers on a quotient scale. Such cases, however, are extremely rare in statistical and econometric research.), i.e., $x_{it}=1, \dots, n$, $x_{jt}=1, \dots, n$ ($t = 1, \dots, n$), then the correlation coefficient (2) transforms into the Spearman coefficient:

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{6 \sum_{t=1}^n d_t^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}, \quad (3)$$

which can be easily proved. In the above formula, d_t denotes the differences between the observations of simultaneous values of a pair of random variables in the form of natural numbers ($t = 1, \dots, n$). As such, coefficient (3) can be used, when

the observations on each pair of the variables are natural numbers belonging to the results of ratio measurement.

Suppose that the observations on variables X and Y form sequences of natural numbers with n observations, that is, $x_i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $y_i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. The sums of the observations on the two variables in such case are as follows (Cf. Steczkowski J., Zeliaś A. (1981): *Statystyczne metody analizy cech jakościowych* [Statistical methods for analysis of qualitative characteristics], PWE, Warszawa, p. 18.):

$$\sum_{i=1}^n x_i = \sum_{i=1}^n y_i = \frac{1}{2}n(n+1). \quad (4)$$

The arithmetic means of the observations on both variables are thus equal:

$$\bar{x} = \bar{y} = \frac{1}{2}(n+1). \quad (5)$$

Moreover,

$$\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n y_i^2 = \frac{1}{6}n(n+1)(2n+1) \quad (6)$$

and

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2 = \frac{1}{12}n(n^2 - 1). \quad (7)$$

Using formulas (4) – (7), the following equality can be easily demonstrated:

$$r_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (x_{it} - \bar{x}_i)(x_{jt} - \bar{x}_j)}{\sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^n (x_{it} - \bar{x}_i)^2 (x_{jt} - \bar{x}_j)^2}} = 1 - \frac{6 \sum_{t=1}^n d_t^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}. \quad (8)$$

Application of the Spearman correlation coefficient for a pair of variables with natural number observations is therefore equivalent to the use of the Pearson correlation coefficient.

Measurement scales

For more than a quarter of a century, awareness of the existence of four measurement scales (measurement is addressed by metrology - a field of science, knowledge and technology covering everything related to measurement. "The subject matter of metrology encompasses all phases of measurement: establishment of a model of the object being measured and of what is being measured (measurand), design and development of a measurement system, execution of the measurement, and elaboration of the measurement result, including identification of the parameters characterizing measurement inaccuracy. Metrology covers determination of the measurement units" [translated from the original in polish]. Cf.: *Encyklopedia gazety wyborczej*, vol. 10, compiled by polish scientific publishers Pwn, Kraków 2004, p. 628.) has been taking shape among the economist circles. Listing the scales according to the strength of numbers, i.e., from the weakest to the strongest, the following scales can be distinguished (The theory of measurement scales was developed by S. S. Stevens and published in his work: *On the Theory of Scales Measurement*, „Science”, Vol. 103, No. 2684/1946.):

- nominal,
- ordinal (rank),
- interval,
- quotient (ratio).

Scales: nominal and ordinal, belong to the weak category, while the other two make up a group of strong scales. Weak scales are primarily used to measure phenomena and processes of qualitative (descriptive) nature. They can also be used to transform strong scale measurement results, in order to eliminate unnecessary excess of information.

Measurement in weak scales

The numbers which we deal with nowadays most often belong to nominal scale measurement results. They act as identifiers, which allow to distinguish between various objects or the characteristics thereof. People are described by such numbers since the very moment of birth. The first such number is the PESEL number, associated with the date of birth. Entering adulthood, each citizen receives a Tax Identification Number (NIP), assigned by the revenue service. When in schools and colleges, students are assigned student ID numbers / student registration numbers. Phone users are assigned corresponding phone numbers, etc.

In a *nominal scale*, numbers are used to mark, identify or classify disparate categories (This issue has been widely discussed in the work: Wiśniewski J. W., *Ekonometryczne badanie zjawisk jakościowych. Studium metodologiczne* [Econometric study of qualitative phenomena. A methodological study], Nicolaus Copernicus University, Toruń, 1986, Chapter I.). The resulting numbers act as symbols, usually replacing names or verbal descriptions. Permissible relations between numbers in this scale exclusively entail: a) an equality of the elements within distinguished categories, e.g., $a = b$; or b) an inequality of disjoint categories, e.g., $b \neq c$. The only arithmetic procedure acceptable is counting, which essentially results in a natural number. In terms of statistical techniques, only those based on counting are allowed.

With regard to nominal scales, attention is drawn to a special case - a dichotomous scale, which is commonly used in statistical research to isolate pairs of disjoint categories. Simultaneous definition of variant A of the phenomenon under consideration enables event classification in a variant form: A or $\bar{A}$ (not A). Assignment of the number 1 to each observation A, and the number 0 to observation $\bar{A}$, results in the so-called zero-one variable.

In an ordinal scale, numbers are ranks, denoting the order of elements or the properties of a phenomenon. The ranks represent not only the elements' equality or inequality, but also their ordering with respect to the property under consideration. The categories of the phenomenon considered are disjoint in this case. Numbers on this scale are comparable in terms of the modulus. Nevertheless, they have relative (not absolute) significance only, for the distances between the ranks are not known. What is more, the distances between adjacent ranks are not equal. It is therefore possible to compare the ranks, by finding both equality relations as well as 'greater than' and, what follows, 'less than' relations, e.g., $a > b > c > \dots > z$. There is no way to determine the distance between the ranks, that is, to establish how much they differ.

It is worth noting the possibility of *objective* and *subjective* measurement. Existence of a standard, to which the object or characteristic measured is compared, allows for an objective measurement result. Such cases are encountered at measurements that produce results expressed in physical units, e.g., weight, length, volume, value in monetary units. Lack of a precisely defined standard results in measurements of subjective character. Any attribute measurements based on asking the respondents to categorize given characteristics in terms of e.g., importance, providing results in the form of ranks, belong to subjective categories.

Arithmetic operations on numbers in various scales

Any arithmetic operation (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division) is permitted on series of numbers with the following characteristics:

- a) the natural zero for a given attribute is known,
- b) the distances between the numbers are known,
- c) the distances between adjacent numbers are unitary and identical for each adjacent pair.

All these properties are possessed only by numbers belonging to the results of ratio (quotient) measurement. Division in particular requires the series to possess each of the properties listed above. Unknown natural zero in a series prevents determination of the ratio of a pair of numbers. For instance, Celsius scale temperature results do not allow for two temperatures to be compared as a quotient. If, on a given day (at a certain place), the temperature at 10 a.m. was 6° C, while on the previous day it was only 3° C at that hour, it cannot be concluded that the temperature on that day was twice as high as the day before. It can only be concluded that the temperature on that day was 3° C higher than the previous day, for the measurement result belong to an interval scale (In statistics and econometrics, the following operations are sometimes carried out: random variable normalization or standardization, resulting in the appearance of a ‘new’ zero in the statistical series, which is not a natural zero. As such, the normalized and the standardized variables belongs to interval measurement results, with all the consequences of this state of affairs), on which the natural zero is unknown.

Addition and subtraction require conditions b and c, i.e., equal, unitary distances between adjacent numbers, to be met. Imagine a sequence of digits together forming a number: 566114602, where in the first case, the number represents net sales revenue of a joint-stock company (in PLN), in the second, it is the number given to an adult Chinese citizen based on the ordering by height, and in the third situation, it is the telephone number for the Department of Econometrics and Statistics at the Nicolaus Copernicus University. The same set of numbers, yet how different the meanings of each of the above numbers and the variety of analytical possibilities. The sales revenue value belongs to a quotient scale, which allows application of all arithmetic operations on a set of such numbers. The number in the ordering by height belongs to rank measurement

results and merely means that 566114602 Chinese citizens are taller (or not shorter) than the person indicated. No arithmetic operations on such numbers are permissible. The phone number, in turn, is only an identifier, allowing the person to whom it is assigned to be contacted; this number belongs to nominal measurement results.

Let us focus on the results of rank measurement. A classic case of objective existence of ranks is the so-called uniformed services (army, police, fire department, etc.). Let us try to analyze the reasonability of summing up military ranks. A colonel, as a rule, must wait a long time for promotion to the rank of a general, and only some officers of this rank become generals. Let us assume that the operation of rank addition is permissible. In such situation, a father with the rank of a colonel could enroll his son in a non-commissioned officer school, allowing him to obtain the rank of a corporal. After obtaining the rank of a corporal, the son abandons his rank to his father, for whom addition of the rank of a corporal opens the possibility of obtaining the rank of a general. Is there any logic in this? Only apparent. Such an operation is impossible, for ranks are not additive. Note the varying distance between different military ranks. The distance between a brigadier general and a general is much greater than the distance between a second lieutenant and a lieutenant, although in both cases, we are dealing with rank adjacency. Summation of ranks, therefore, leads to absurd results. This means that determination of the arithmetic mean given by formula (5) is not permissible for a number of ranks.

Subtraction of ranks can lead to absurdity as well. It is only permissible to determine the number of ranks to be climbed, from a certain rank to the target rank. For instance, in order for a captain to achieve the rank of a brigadier general, he/she must obtain four successive promotions to the ranks of a major, a lieutenant

colonel and a colonel, to ultimately become a general. It is recognized that the higher the rank, the harder it is to achieve. There is no linearity here, which would allow for any addition or subtraction of ranks. The fundamental issue, however, entails the lack of knowledge of the distances between the ranks, which prevents any arithmetic operations.

Example of spearman correlation coefficient application

The results of a rank measurement can essentially emerge in two ways. First - they can be obtained directly, by ordering the random variable of a rank nature. Second - ranks can arise from the transformation of strong scale measurement results, through giving up some of the information that was contained in a variable belonging, for example, to a quotient scale.

Let us consider measurement of the correlation between trader productivity (y_i) and his/her age (x_i). The value of the Pearson correlation coefficient for this pair of variables is $r_{yx} = 0.5938$. The original variables have been transformed into ranks, whilst the traders were ordered by performance (y_{li}), from the highest to the lowest. The by-age ordering of traders (x_{li}) has been arranged from the oldest (rank 1) to the youngest (rank 30). The Spearman correlation coefficient value calculated for this pair of variables is $r_{y_1x_1}^{(S)} = 0.8509$. The Pearson correlation coefficient value for this pair of rank variables $r_{y_1x_1}^{(P)} = 0.8509 = r_{y_1x_1}^{(S)}$ was calculated as well. It turns out that the use of the Pearson coefficient is sufficient to simultaneously obtain a result for the Spearman correlation coefficient. Note that after removing some of the information on the original variables (y_i, x_i), by using the variables expressed in a rank form (y_{li}, x_{li}), the measure of the correlation between productivity and age increased from the level of 0.5938 to 0.8509. The resulting transformation of the original variables into ranks leads to a clearly different level of the correlation thereof (It may happen that the sign of the correlation coefficient changes as a

result of the replacement of the original variables by ranks, which implies a radical change, leading to a cognitive error). Transformation of variables, from a strong scale to a rank scale, should thus be approached with great caution.

Table 1. Net sales revenues of MAX company traders from 2009 to 2011 (in thousand PLN)

Trader no. (i)	y_i (thousand PLN)	Y_{li} (ranks)	x_i (years)	X_{li} (ranks)
1	912	30	25	28
2	930	29	23	30
3	933	28	25	27
4	940	27	27	25
5	945	26	26	26
6	950	25	29	24
7	952	24	24	29
8	955	23	39	15
9	960	22	30	23
10	966	21	33	20
11	967	20	34	19
12	968	19	31	22
13	970	18	32	21
14	985	17	36	18
15	990	16	40	14
16	992	15	43	12
17	998	14	45	10
18	1000	13	46	9
19	1020	12	56	1
20	1025	11	54	2
21	1030	10	49	6
22	1060	9	37	17
23	1100	8	38	16
24	1160	7	44	11
25	1204	6	50	5
26	1260	5	41	13
27	1304	4	51	4
28	1406	3	52	3
29	1511	2	47	8
30	1620	1	48	7
Σ	32013	465	1155	465

Source: stipulated data

Statistical tools permissible in weak scales

Many scientific works address addition and subtraction of ranks, determination of arithmetic mean or variance, etc., while only various statistical tools that are based on positional measures are allowed for ranks. Fractionation instruments, including appropriate statistical tests, are thus permitted. Rank measurement, in turn, does not allow for explicit use of correlation and regression analysis tools, due to the inadmissibility of arithmetic operations on numbers of this class.

A question arises, therefore, of whether in the case of rank measurement researchers are helpless in the face of the questions posed regarding attribute interdependence or correlation? One effective solution may be to convert ranks into zero-one variables. This allows for analysis of attribute association (associations, counter associations). Suppose that a study of consumer behavior is being conducted, and the consumers are expected to rank the importance of certain product features. The results obtained for a specific feature (e.g., product durability) can be associated, for instance, with the respondents' education (It is worth noting that the measurement results obtained for both variables are subjective in nature. The lack of a standard and one's subjective feeling determine the importance of product durability to the consumer. The variety of bachelor's and higher diplomas results in a clear heterogeneity of the observation results on the variable characterizing the respondent's education.). Transformation of the ranks into a zero-one variable, so that number 1 is assigned to those observations on the variable X_j , for which the respondent indicated (In this case, the variable X_j obviously expresses the importance of product durability to the respondent) ranks 1, 2 or 3, i.e.:

$$x_{tj} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{when the rank is 1, 2 or 3,} \\ 0, & \text{in other cases} \end{cases}$$

where t is the statistical observation's number (respondent's number), ($t = 1, \dots, n$). To test the association between product durability preference and the consumer's level of education, a specific level (type) of education must be distinguished, using another zero-one variable X_i , identifying type A education (e.g., college education, a bachelor's degree at the very least), that is, e.g.:

$$x_{ti} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{for respondents at level A,} \\ 0, & \text{in other cases.} \end{cases}$$

In such a case, based on the below bivariate table, the following attribute association coefficient (9) can be used:

$$r_{ij} = \frac{A + B - (C + D)}{n\sqrt{(n_{11} + n_{10})(n_{00} + n_{01})(n_{00} + n_{10})(n_{11} + n_{01})}}, \quad (9)$$

where:

$$A = n_{00}(n_{11} + n_{10})(n_{11} + n_{01}),$$

$$B = n_{11}(n_{00} + n_{01})(n_{00} + n_{10}),$$

$$C = n_{10}(n_{00} + n_{01})(n_{11} + n_{01}),$$

$$D = n_{01}(n_{11} + n_{01})(n_{00} + n_{10}).$$

Association coefficient (9) has been transformed from the Pearson correlation coefficient, for the purpose of frequency analysis (Cf. J. Churgin, *Jak policzyć niepoliczalne* [How to count the uncountable], Wiedza Powszechna, Warszawa, 1985, pp. 20 – 28.) . It reaches classical values, i.e., $-1 \leq r_{ij} \leq 1$. It is also possible to test the significance of this association coefficient.

Transformation of rank measurement results into zero-one variables (A shift to nominal scale measurement, resulting in a loss of some information, but increasing the analytical possibilities) increases the applicability of statistic and

econometric tools, compared to the potential of a rank scale. Having measurement results in the form of zero-one variables also allows for the use of regression models, for aggregate data especially (Cf. J. W. Wiśniewski (1986), Subchapter 4.2 and Chapter 6, as well as (2009), Subchapter 6.6). It is therefore worth comparing the benefits of increased analytical capabilities in nominal scales, in terms of zero-one measurement, against the loss of some of the information contained in the ranks.

Table 2. Aggregate counts of observations on the pair of zero-one X_i and X_j

Zero-one variable		X_j		Total
		$x_{tj} = 0$	$x_{tj} = 1$	
X_i	$x_{ti} = 0$	n_{00}	n_{01}	$n_{00} + n_{01} = q_i$
	$x_{ti} = 1$	n_{10}	n_{11}	$n_{10} + n_{11} = p_i$
Total		$n_{00} + n_{10} = q_j$	$n_{01} + n_{11} = p_j$	$n = q_i + p_i = p_j + q_j$

Source: Wiśniewski J. W., *Ekonometryczne badanie zjawisk jakościowych*.

Studium metodologiczne [Econometric study of qualitative phenomena. A methodological study], UMK, Toruń, 1986, pp. 59 – 60

Conclusion

It has long been known that the Spearman correlation coefficient is a special case of the Pearson correlation coefficient. The Spearman case concerns a pair of sequences of natural numbers, which inherently belong to ratio scale measurement results. The physical similarity of a sequence of n natural numbers to a sequence of n ranks results in the erroneous treatment of ranks as strong scale measurement results. As such, the Spearman correlation coefficient is commonly misused in the literature as a rank correlation coefficient. This fails to recognize the equivalence of the Spearman's and Pearson's correlation coefficients. Treating the Spearman correlation coefficient as a rank correlation coefficient results in direct application

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